

NOTES

TABLE 1—TITRATIONS CONDITIONS FOR DIFFERENT METAL IONS

Metal ions	pH	Optimum concentration mg/20 ml	Buffer	Colour change	Temperature °C	Standard Deviation
Zinc(II)	3.0-4.8	0.326 to 10.462	Ac/HAc	B-Y	0 to 50	0.003
Cadmium(II)	5.8-7.5	0.381 to 11.242	hexamine/HNO ₃	B-Y	45 to 95	0.007
Mercury(II)	5.8-7.5	1.003 to 200 mg	hexamine/HNO ₃	B-YO	0 to 70	0.006

Where B=Blue, Y=Yellow, YO=Yellow Orange.

estimation chloride ion can be tolerated in large amounts in presence of silver nitrate. This fact has been made use of in masking bismuth(III) with chloride, the excess of which can be removed by adding silver nitrate.

Determination of zinc(II) in presence of cadmium(II) or mercury(II) :

Since iodide interferes seriously in case of cadmium(II) and mercury(II) estimations, the fact has been utilized in determining zinc(II) in presence of cadmium(II) or mercury(II). The procedure adopted is as follows :

To a suitable aliquot containing 1.307 mg of zinc(II) and varying amounts of cadmium or mercury or both add 1 ml 10% KI, followed by two drops of LANAS solution. Dilute the solution to 20 ml and titrate according to recommended procedure. It has been observed that Zn(II) could be titrated successfully in presence of double the amount of Cd(II) or Hg(II) when present together or above in a mixture. The percentage error was found to be ≤ 0.5 .

LANAS thus works as a good metallochromic indicator for three metal ions. Zinc(II) could be determined in presence of cadmium and mercury successfully.

Acknowledgement

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A Study on Conductance of Manganese Soaps in Isobutanol and Benzaldehyde

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TRANSITION metal soaps are well known as catalytic agents^{1,2} and also find applications in the preparation of greases³⁻⁵. In view of the importance of these soaps, it was found to be of interest to study their physical properties in different solvents. Recently the conductance behaviour of these soaps inferred that soaps form micellar aggregates in water⁶ and alcohols^{7,8}. In the present investigation, we have studied the conductance of manganese soaps (laurate, caprate and caprylate) in isobutanol and benzaldehyde at different temperatures in order to (i) determine the CMC of the soap solutions, (ii) confirm the effect of temperature if any on CMC and (iii) determine dissociation constant, K, molecular conductance at infinite dilution, λ_{∞} , activation energy of conductance, ΔE_{λ} and heat of dissociation, ΔH° .

Experimental

Isobutanol, benzaldehyde, manganese chloride, *n*-caprylic, capric and lauric acids (Merck or B.D.H. reagent grade) were used. The fatty acids were purified by distillation under reduced pressure, the purity being confirmed by b.p. measurements.

The preparation of the soaps and measurement of conductivity were described in the previous communication⁹. The reproducibility of the results was examined by repeating the measurements.

Results and Discussion

Specific conductance, k, of soap solutions (Table 1) increases with increasing concentration as

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well as temperature. The plots (Fig. 1) of k vs C are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a definite concentration corresponding to CMC (Table 2). The values of CMC are independent of temperature but decrease with increasing chain length of the soap. It is seen that these values in both the solvents are found the same from this technique.

TABLE 1—SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE, k OF MANGANESE LAURATE IN ISOBUTANOL AT TEMPERATURES 35-50°

Conc. of Soap in moles litre ⁻¹	$k \times 10^6$ in ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹			
	35°	40°	45°	50°
0.008	1.777	1.794	1.814	1.832
.004	1.965	2.015	2.030	2.049
.005	2.175	2.220	2.255	2.310
.006	2.430	2.474	2.520	2.575
.008	2.769	2.344	2.913	2.986
.010	2.978	3.065	3.150	3.225
.012	3.195	3.315	3.385	3.460
.015	3.528	3.664	3.736	3.810

Fig. 1. Plot of specific conductance, (ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹) k vs concentration (moles litre⁻¹), C of manganese laurate in benzaldehyde at temperatures 35-50°.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF CMC, HEAT OF DISSOCIATION, ΔH° AND AVERAGE VALUES OF ACTIVATION ENERGY OF CONDUCTANCE, ΔE_λ FOR MANGANESE SOAPS IN ISOBUTANOL AND BENZALDEHYDE AT TEMPERATURE 35-50°

Solvent	Soap	CMC (moles litre ⁻¹)	ΔH° (k.cals mole ⁻¹)	ΔE_λ (k.cals.mole ⁻¹)	
				Above CMC	Below CMC
Isobutanol	Laurate	0.008	15.59	1.60	1.14
	Caprate	0.009	28.42	1.37	0.91
	Caprylate	0.010	28.87	1.14	0.90
Benzaldehyde	Laurate	0.008	—	1.60	0.91
	Caprate	0.009	—	1.49	0.91
	Caprylate	0.010	—	1.38	0.68

Molecular conductance, λ_M decreases with increase in concentration of the soap solution. The plots (Fig. 2) of λ_M vs $C^{1/2}$ are concave upwards

Fig. 2. Plot of molecular conductance λ_M (ohm⁻¹cm²moles⁻¹) vs square root of concentration, $C^{1/2}$ of manganese laurate in isobutanol at temperatures 35-50°.

indicating the weak electrolyte behaviour of these soaps. When $\log \lambda_M$ was plotted against $\log C$ a linear plot is observed.

This shows that the conductance behaviour of soap solutions may be represented (Fig. 3) by an equation

$$\log \lambda_M = A + B \log C \quad \dots (i)$$

Fig. 3. Plot of $-\log \lambda_M$ vs $-\log C$ of manganese soaps in benzaldehyde at 35°.

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where, A and B are constants and C is the concentration of soap solutions in moles litre⁻¹.

Constant—A (Table 3) in isobutanol is higher than benzaldehyde, varying with the soap at different temperatures in the order :

Laurate > caprate > caprylate

Constant B (Table 3) is found to decrease regularly with temperature in isobutanol and approximately so in benzaldehyde. However, these values in benzaldehyde are higher than isobutanol.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF CONSTANTS—A AND B OF MANGANESE SOAP SOLUTIONS IN ISOBUTANOL AND BENZALDEHYDE AT TEMPERATURES 35-50°

Solvent	Temperature (°C)	Laurate		Caprate		Caprylate	
		-A	B	-A	B	-A	B
Isobutanol	35	1.72	0.60	2.66	0.68	2.70	0.66
	40	1.66	.58	2.54	.64	2.58	.62
	45	1.58	.54	2.50	.62	2.54	.60
	50	1.54	.52	2.44	.58	2.50	.56
Benzaldehyde	35	1.66	0.86	2.04	0.72	2.10	0.74
	40	1.58	.82	2.02	.70	2.08	.72
	45	1.56	.82	2.00	.70	2.04	.72
	50	1.46	.78	1.90	.68	2.02	.70

The effect of temperature on the conductance may be discussed by an expression :

$$\lambda_M = A' e^{-\Delta E_\lambda / RT} \quad \dots (ii)$$

where A' and ΔE_λ are constants.

It may be pointed out that constant ΔE_λ is of importance, since information can be obtained on aggregation by measuring the activation energy of conductance. The values of ΔE_λ , has been calculated from the slopes of the linear plots of $\log \lambda_M$ vs $1/T$. It is seen that there is a large difference in the values of ΔE_λ (Table 2) below and above CMC which supports the micellar behaviour of manganese soaps.

Manganese soap has been reported to behave as a weak electrolyte in dilute solutions, the dissociation of soaps can thus be derived^{9,10} as follows :

$$K = \frac{4C^2\alpha^3}{1-\alpha} \quad \dots (iv)$$

The degree of dissociation, α , of soaps in solution is very small. Ionic concentration would be low and interionic effects can be neglected. On replacing $\alpha = \lambda_M / \lambda_\infty$ and rearranging, we obtain

$$C^2 \lambda_M^2 = \frac{K \lambda_\infty^3}{4 \lambda_M} - \frac{\lambda_\infty^3 K}{4} \quad \dots (v)$$

The plots of $C^2 \lambda_M^2$ vs $1/\lambda_M$ are linear below CMC and the equation fails above this concentration in isobutanol. The values of λ_∞ and K, calculated from equation (v) at different temperatures are given in Table 4. These values in benzaldehyde could not be obtained because equation (v) fails completely in this solvent.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF MOLECULAR CONDUCTANCE AT INFINITE DILUTION, λ_∞ AND DISSOCIATION CONSTANT, K OF MANGANESE SOAP SOLUTIONS IN ISOBUTANOL AT TEMPERATURES 35-50°

Temperature in °C	Laurate		Caprate		Caprylate	
	λ_∞	$K \times 10^6$	λ_∞	$K \times 10^6$	λ_∞	$K \times 10^6$
35	1.479	0.042	0.250	32.000	0.359	0.099
40	1.619	0.032	0.375	11.380	0.458	.046
45	1.947	.020	0.500	4.799	0.575	.024
50	2.177	.012	0.670	2.040	0.719	.014

Molecular conductance at infinite dilution, λ_∞ increases with increase in temperature. The rise in temperature causes increase in ionic mobility despite the fact that the addition of the soap increases the viscosity of the solvent.

The dissociation constant, K, decreases with increase in temperature and decrease in dielectric constant of the solvent. In a medium of low dielectric constant, the electrostatic attractive forces between positive and negative ions are large, giving rise to a diminished small dissociation.

The heat of dissociation, ΔH° has been calculated in isobutanol from the slopes of the plots of $\log K$ vs $1/T$ and is given in Table 2. It is seen that the values of ΔH° decrease with increase in the chain length of soap.

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Anion Exchange Studies of Metal Ions in Aqueous NH₄SCN-DMSO Mixed Solvent Systems

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DOWEX macroporous MSA-1 resin has been used to obtain rapid exchange equilibria. The distribution coefficients of Cr(III), Fe(III), In(III), Hg(II), Cd(II), Zn(II), Co(II), Mn(II), Tl(I) and Ag(I) have been measured by batch process and using radiotracer technique. These measurements have been made in different concentrations (0.1M-5.0M) of aqueous ammonium thiocyanate and in different volume percentages (0-80) of dimethyl sulfoxide at overall one molar concentration of ammonium thiocyanate solution. The effect of DMSO in mixed solvent systems has been studied.

DMSO is a useful solvent for ion exchange studies because it shows some specific selectivities which have not yet been explained. It has high dielectric constant and a strong solvating tendency for metal ions. Numerous studies have therefore been made in DMSO-HCl^{1,2} and DMSO-HNO₃^{3,4} systems. Ammonium thiocyanate is a strong complexing agent which forms a large number of complexes with metal ions. It will be interesting to replace these ligands by thiocyanate in these studies. The preferential uptake of metal-DMSO or metal-thiocyanate complex by the resin opens a new interest. Turner *et al*⁵ investigated the behaviour of some 3d transition metals on Dowex-1 resin in KSCN solutions. Some of the metal ions could not be eluted from the column during the separation. Then some other workers tried NH₄SCN-HCl^{6,7} media using weakly basic⁸ and cellulose⁹ resins. Recently Singh and Tandon¹⁰ studied the anion exchange behaviour of some metal ions in thiocyanate-organic solvent mixed systems. They used acetone, methanol or ThE as organic solvent. As far as we are aware no anion exchange study has been reported in aqueous thiocyanate-DMSO mixed solvent system. We have therefore tried to investigate the ion exchange and DMSO behaviour in

these mixed solvent systems. Some interesting separations have also been developed using distribution data.

Experimental

Apparatus and Chemicals : Na(I) (Tl) well type scintillation counter was used for gamma countings of Cr(51), Mn(54), Co(58), Fe(59), Zn(65), Ag(110m), In(114 m) and Hg(203). Beta countings of Cd and Tl were done on a Geiger M Counter.

The macroporous resin (Dowex MSA-1), 20-50 mesh, Cl-form was received from Sigma Chemical Co.(USA) as a gift. All metal sulphates or nitrates were of BDH AnalaR grade. Metal tracers were collected from BARC, Trombay (India). The DMSO was from J. T. Baker Co., Phillipsburg. The ammonium thiocyanate was of BDH AnalaR grade.

The resin was converted into thiocyanate form by treating it with 5M NaOH followed by 20% KSCN solution for 3 days with intermittent shaking. The resin was then washed with water and then dried. The ion exchange capacity was found 3.9 meq/g.

The Kd values were determined by batch process. In this process the exactly weighed 0.5 g resin were added into 50 ml stoppered conical flasks which contained 2 × 10⁻² meq metal ion in 10 ml solvent mixtures. The content was allowed to stand for 16 hours with intermittent shaking. The resin was filtered and 2 ml of the filtrate from each flask was counted on the gamma counter⁸. This counting was treated as final counting, C_f. The initial counting, C_i was taken with blank solution in which the resin was not taken. For Beta countings, the 2 ml portion of the filtrate or the blank was dried over a red lamp in a planchet and counted on Beta counter. The Kd value was then calculated as

$$Kd = \frac{C_i - C_f}{C_f} \times 50 \text{ (ml/g)}$$

The separations were achieved by column equilibrium method. In this method, a 4 cm column (i.d. 0.8 cm) was packed with the resin. After conditioning, the column was eluted with 2 ml fractions of eluent at a flow rate of 10 ml/h. The collected fractions were then counted and converted into the concentrations.

Results and Discussion

The curves in Fig. 1 show some interesting aspects.

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